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Planting date effects on the dynamics of the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), and the damage status of roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) plants in Luxor, Egypt

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Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) is an important crop, but the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), hampers its economic production. The purpose of this study was to assess the effects of different roselle planting dates on the abundance and damage status of mealybugs. The study was conducted during two growing seasons, 2022 and 2023, in a private farm of Balady roselle cultivar in the Esna region, Luxor Governorate, Egypt. Four different times, on April 14th, April 29th, May 13th, and May 27th, we cultivated the roselle plants in the field. The findings showed that later roselle planting was associated with a higher percentage of damaged leaves and a higher density of mealybug populations. Using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multivariate statistical analyses (Principal component analysis, dendrogram from cluster analysis, and hierarchical clustering), the results revealed a clear variation in *P. solenopsis* populations between planting dates within each season; the first planting date on April 14th was significantly different from all other planting dates. The early planting date showed a decrease in *P. solenopsis* population dynamics across both seasons compared to the late planting date. Furthermore, these results support the idea that a significant decrease in mealybug populations was associated with the early planting date of April 14th, while the insect population trend increased significantly with subsequent planting dates (The third and fourth planting dates) in both seasons. The heatmap and hierarchical clustering also supported similar relationships between planting dates that shared the seven assessed characteristics. The data from the similarity coefficient matrix was used to create a dendrogram. A dendrogram was constructed using the similarity coefficient matrix data. The early planting date showed a significant decrease in *P. solenopsis* numbers, percentage of damaged leaves, and all measures of dispersal and attraction, except for a higher non-preference index. Conversely, the fourth planting date showed the highest significant increase in *P. solenopsis* numbers, percentage of damaged leaves, and measures of dispersal and attraction, except for a lower non-preference index. These findings show that early roselle planting dates can be a useful tactic for sustainable crop management, as they can reduce cotton mealybug damage in an efficient, non-chemical way.

Introduction

Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.), classified in the Malvaceae family, is an important multipurpose plant cultivated for its calyces, leaves, and stems, which can be used as a source of food, medicine, and fiber (Ismail *et al.*, 2020). Though roselle is an economically important crop, it faces many challenges to production from multiple insect pests (Abdel Moniem and Abd El-Wahab, 2006).

Among those pests, the mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), is a serious threat and is considered a harmful pest on roselle (Vennila *et al.*, 2011). It feeds on the phloem sap of the host, and it begins attacking soft shoots, twigs, leaf veins, branches, and fruits (Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2010). This pest attacks all growth stages of the plant from germination to harvest (Aheer *et al.*, 2009). The feeding damage caused by *P. solenopsis* to the leaves, branches, and fruits can lead to sap loss and a serious impact on the plant (Shehata, 2017, and Bakry and Aljedani, 2023). Feeding damage from mealybugs can constitute chlorosis, distorted leaves, death of growth tips, early leaf drop, dryness, dwarfing, wrinkles, stunted growth, deformation, leaf drop, and death of plants (Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2013, and Bakry *et al.*, 2023). The prolonged nutrient deprivation can limit plant growth and roselle yield (Saad, 2021). It infests the roselle plants, and because it directly feeds on sap from the plant leaf, feeds on significant amounts of phloem sap, and produces large amounts of honeydew, it encourages the presence and activity of ants (Elbahrawy *et al.*, 2020). The insect's large numbers, decreased mobility, and concentrated consumption of nymphs reduce the vigour, growth, and yield of plant growth (Sahayaraj *et al.*, 2014).

Environmental circumstances, host plant phenology, and the existence of

natural enemies are some of the elements that affect mealybug population dynamics (Sadek *et al.*, 2023). These factors have led to a greater focus on integrated pest management (IPM) solutions, which include non-chemical control approaches. By altering the life cycle of the pest and/or reducing its population to less economically destructive levels, cultural techniques, including moderate early planting, offer promise as sustainable solutions to minimize losses (Baqir, 2024).

Cultural practices, especially planting date in crops such as roselle, can play an important role in pest management, such as diversifying the timing of the growth stages of a crop versus the pest population peak. As demonstrated in the literature, if the planting date is optimal, it is likely to mitigate pest infestation and allow for improved yields. In the case of roselle in particular, it can be demonstrated that early planting enhances vegetative growth parameters, thus increasing yield and its components, especially if timed to coincide with the planting window of May 22nd, as compared to late planting dates (Amin, 2020).

Previous studies on other crops have shown that adjusting planting dates can be a simple and effective way to reduce pest pressure. Furthermore, early planting can disrupt the life cycle timing of both host plant and pest, which can lead to reduced pest infestation (Asif *et al.*, 2023). In this case, early planting on June 4th saw more fruit per plant (43.6%) than in later dates but also produced higher biomass and sepal yields, which were 395.33 kg/ha (Gholam and Moosavi, 2012). Modifying planting dates can similarly alter life cycle timing, as shown in the case of cotton. Compared to later planting, early planting produced a higher yield and noticeably reduced levels of pests, including

bollworms and jassids (Asif *et al.*, 2023).

Araujo *et al.* (2019) mentioned that the planting window is the time at which peach crops are planted in relation to the time of pest population. Predicting pest abundance population cycles is critical for sustainable pest management. The aim of this research was to evaluate the effect of different planting dates on mealybug prevalence and damage status of roselle plants.

Materials and methods

1. Population abundance of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on four roselle planting dates:

1.1. Study site:

In order to assess the effect of sowing dates on the incidence of mealybugs, weekly inspections were carried out in a planted area of private roselle (Balady cv.) (25°23'45" N, 32°36'60" E) in Esna District, Luxor region, Egypt. The roselle plants were sown on four consecutive dates spaced two weeks apart from April 14th to May 27th throughout the two growing seasons (Years 2022 and 2023).

1.2. Experimental Design:

The experimental field was around 2100 square meters in size and was separated into four sections, each measuring 525 square meters. There are four planting dates for hibiscus in the growing season: April 14th, April 29th, May 13th, and May 27th. The dates were selected to reflect a variety of growing season environmental variables. Four replicates were used for each planting date in the Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) experiment. All common agricultural procedures, including fertilization and irrigation in all tested planting dates, were applied consistently to every plot (Replicate).

1.3. Data collection:

After planting roselle seeds at each of the four different planting dates, pest monitoring began at 10:00 a.m. Sampling began from each plot

(replication) as soon as germination was observed on the soil layer and continued every week until the roselle plant was harvested for each date.

1.4. The main parameters measured were:

1.4.1. Study of the population density of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* individuals per leaf:

The total estimates of mealybugs were calculated on forty randomly selected hibiscus leaves from two seasons and at different levels of roselle plants (Ten leaves per replication) from each plot. The pests were stored in tubes filled with 90% alcohol and transported to the Plant Protection Research Institute, affiliated with the Agricultural Research Centre in Giza, Egypt, for classification of this pest. These leaves were collected, placed in separate plastic bags, and transported to the laboratory. Under a binocular microscope, the total number of *P. solenopsis* (Nymphs and adults) on both surfaces (Upper and lower) of the leaves was counted and estimated for population density (Bakry and Fathipour, 2023). Over the two cropping seasons, we collected 7680 leaves in total, or 48 distinct observation times. Four planting dates × four duplicates × twenty-four times × ten leaves × two seasons were used. Each season had 3840 leaves. In addition to the weekly monitoring, a direct inspection of mealybugs was conducted (Bakry and Arbab 2020, and Bakry, 2022).

1.4.2. The proportion of damaged leaves:

Any leaves that exhibit symptoms of a mealybug infestation, such as honeydew, sooty mould, or leaf curl, are considered damaged. The percentage of damaged leaves is calculated by dividing the number of damaged leaves in the sample under examination by the total number of leaves seen on each investigation date (attacked +

uninjured). This method is applied by Bakry and Abdel-Baky (2023).

1.5. Statistical analysis:

To ascertain the statistical significance of the variations in the planting dates, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on the gathered data. The means of the treatments were compared using Tukey's HSD post-hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$), which was calculated with the MSTATC Program Soft (Freed, 1991).

2. Evaluating the indicators of prevalence and attraction:

2.1. Mealybug quantity ratio (QR):

Measuring the number of mealybugs present on a leaf. It is calculated as the number of pest individuals at each planting date divided by the number of pests estimates at each planting date in 100 (Tu *et al.*, 2018).

2.2. Mealybug attraction index (AI):

In this case, A is the number of mealybugs in each planting date, and M is the mean population of mealybugs for each planting date. If $AI > 1$, it shows a high preference; if $AI = 1$, it shows a mean preference; and if $AI < 1$, it shows a low preference (Krisnawati *et al.*, 2017).

$$AI = \frac{2A}{M + A}$$

2.3. Mealybug crowding intensity (M*):

An ecological index used to deal with the dispersion patterns of larvae (Lloyd, 1967). In this equation, \bar{x} and S^2 are the mean and variance of population estimates in each planting date studied, respectively.

$$M * = \bar{x} + \frac{s^2}{\bar{x} + 1}$$

2.4. Mealybug non-preference index (NPI):

$$NPI = \left[\frac{100 - R}{100 + R} \right] \times 100$$

Where R is the mean mealybug estimate for every planting date in relation to the mean total mealybug estimate for the planting dates (Antônio *et al.*, 2011).

2.5. Mealybug prevalence index (PI):

This index measures the hibiscus planting date at which the pest preferred to attack the plant. In this case, P is the mean mealybug estimate for all planting dates evaluated, and T is the mean number of mealybugs in each planting date per sample (Antônio *et al.*, 2011).

$$PI = \frac{(T - P)}{(T + P)} \times 100$$

Through the evaluation of various planting dates for mealybug infestation, these metrics are useful tools that assist researchers in identifying and recommending hibiscus planting dates that are least impacted by mealybugs (Bakry *et al.*, 2025).

3. Multivariate estimation methods:

In an attempt to quantify planting date and variable relationships and their efficiencies better, two multivariate statistical methods were used.

3.1. Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

PCA was one of these multivariate analytical techniques to uncover latent relationships and patterns, and it was conducted in order to lower the data dimensionality on information pertaining to four planting times, based upon mean numbers of mealybugs per leaf (Wambi *et al.*, 2025). To illustrate the multidimensionality of the number of mealybugs per leaf at selected planting dates of interest in a scatterplot in R software, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used (R Core Team, 2023). The two axes of the biplot, principal component 1 (PC1) and principal component 2 (PC2), describe linear combinations of original

variables that retain most of the original variables' variance. The fact that there is a high cumulative proportion of variance explained by PC1 and PC2 means that PC1 and PC2 do an excellent job summarizing, in totality, the variance in this data set (Tang *et al.*, 2021). This method is very useful in illustrating complex interrelationships between planting dates and measured attributes, giving an overall picture of spreading patterns (Getu *et al.*, 2024).

3.2. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis:

3.2.1. Dendrogram from hierarchical cluster analysis of four planting dates was applied to estimate the relationships between numbers of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* individuals per leaf on different roselle planting dates:

Hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) of the unweighted pair-group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) based on the distance between clusters as per the Euclidean distance, under the PAST program (Hammer *et al.*, 2001), was employed. The method facilitated visualization of samples based on the similarity matrix and identification of interrelationships of mealybug counts per leaf in four planting dates. The results were visualized using a dendrogram, where the distance (Dissimilarity) between clusters is represented by the vertical axis, the merging of clusters is depicted by the horizontal lines, and the height of the merge indicates the distance at which they are joined. The numerical values at the top of the dendrogram quantify the distance for each planting date and the overall clustering (Loureiro *et al.*, 2024).

3.2.2. Heat maps and hierarchical clustering were applied for assessing seven indicators of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* population, damage, and their spread observed on various planting dates of roselle:

Seven criteria were evaluated, and planting dates were grouped according to how comparable their performance was throughout the two seasons using the hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) approach. The output is shown in a dendrogram, which provides a graphical display of hierarchical relationships in planting dates. The dendrogram reveals four planting dates having more alike performances aggregated at shorter "distances," signifying more relatedness in their response to infestation, based on R software (R Core Team, 2023).

Results and discussion

1. Effect of differential dates of sowing on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* population and percentage of leaf damage:

In this study, entomological criteria established on various parameters were used to delimit pest density in terms of insect numbers and injured leaf percentages.

1.1. Population ecology of mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

Observations revealed *P. solenopsis* started to emerge fourteen days after planting under all varied planting dates on roselle plants and continued until their harvest over the two seasons. Having mealybug colonies on every leaf was witnessed throughout all planting dates in roselle throughout every season, as represented in Figure (1). The number on average \pm standard error of *P. solenopsis* colonies per leaf throughout all planting times revealed similar figures for seasons 2022 (14.71 ± 0.81) and 2023 (16.42 ± 0.83), respectively. The data illustrated in Figure (1) indicate that the plants sown on the initial date (April 14th) exhibited the lowest presence of *P. solenopsis* individuals, recording 9.02 ± 0.47 and 9.60 ± 0.48 mealybugs per leaf in the 2023 and 2024 growing seasons, respectively. In contrast, the highest average number of *P. solenopsis* across

both seasons was observed in the roselle plants that were planted on the fourth sowing date on May 27th, with counts of 18.74 ± 1.04 and 22.03 ± 1.07 individuals per leaf. Followed by the plants sown on the third date, May 13th, which had 16.60 ± 0.97 and 19.39 ± 1.15 individuals per leaf, while the second sowing date, April 29th, yielded the lowest figures of 14.49 ± 0.95 and 15.84 ± 0.85 individuals per leaf across the two seasons, respectively, as depicted in Figure (1).

This would imply that sowing time has an essential role to play in influencing *P. solenopsis* individual population size, as earlier sown roselle plants have less damage and may prove a better strategy in reducing mealybug numbers. Since it can be observed through the data that growing crops in the later part of the season, i.e., on May 27th, results in an elevated number of *P. solenopsis* individuals, it would be best not to cultivate roselle at this latter time of the season. The average number of mealybug individuals estimated throughout the 2022 season showed a statistically significant difference among the various planting dates of roselle ($F = 169.27$; $df = 285$; $P \leq 0.0000$; coefficient of variation = 21.35%) and in season 2023 ($F = 273.11$; $df = 285$; $P \leq 0.0000$; coefficient of variation = 18.12%). The initial planting day had the lowest mealybug population, whereas the fourth planting date had the highest, as seen by the bar charts (Fig. 1). The significance of these changes is attested by the various statistical letters on the bars. In both seasons, the first planting date received a "B" rating, while the fourth date received an "A" score.

1.2. Percentages of leaves damaged by *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

As can be seen in Figure (1), it was observed that *P. solenopsis* leaf damage rates increased 15 days after planting for all single planting dates of roselle in both seasons. Results indicated that roselle plants of the first and second dates of cultivation experienced lower rates of damaged *P. solenopsis* leaf rates over the two seasons, with averages of $20.42 \pm 0.82\%$ and $22.50 \pm 0.86\%$ on the first date (April 14th) and $29.33 \pm 1.02\%$ and $30.21 \pm 0.99\%$ on the second date (April 29th). The highest percentages of damaged leaves by *P. solenopsis* were observed during the third and fourth times of cultivation (May 13th and May 27th), with averages of $30.73 \pm 1.21\%$ and $31.35 \pm 1.15\%$ on the third date (May 13th) and $33.13 \pm 1.13\%$ and $35.42 \pm 1.15\%$ on the fourth date (May 27th) over the two seasons, respectively. These data showed the highest percentages of leaf damage caused by *P. solenopsis*, as illustrated in Figure (1).

The ranking below shows, in hierarchical order, the performance of the evaluated planting dates based on mealybug counts and percentages of damaged leaf assessed during this study. Fourth date > third date > second date > first date per season. The mean percentage of damaged leaves by *P. solenopsis* for the 2022 season was significantly different amongst the various roselle planting dates ($F = 50.33$; $df = 285$; $P \leq 0.0000$; coefficient of variation = 26.98%) and season 2023 ($F = 52.57$; $df = 285$; $P \leq 0.0000$; coefficient of variation = 24.42%).

Figure (1): Influence of four roselle planting dates on the average count of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* individuals per leaf and the average percentage of damaged leaves measured over the 2022 and 2023 seasons. Applying Tukey's HSD test at $P < 0.05$, differences between planting dates are indicated by the use of different letters both for the number of mealybug individuals and the percentage of damaged leaves.

The findings showed that later planting dates for roselle plants resulted in a larger mealybug population density and a higher proportion of infestation-damaged leaves. On the other hand, the initial planting date had the lowest mealybug population and the lowest proportion of damaged leaves, as illustrated in Figure (2). Later planting dates result in a higher proportion of damaged leaves and an increase in the mealybug counts (Figure 2). This implies that planting roselle early might be a quick and easy way to reduce crop loss and mealybug infestation. Variations in the environmental circumstances surrounding various roselle planting dates might influence mealybug activity and infection levels, which in turn could influence variations in mealybug population estimates. This implies that planting date has a major influence on the proportion of infestation, as early planted roselle plants frequently have lower infestation percentages and may be a more effective way to prevent mealybug *P. solenopsis* infestation. Consequently, it is not recommended to grow roselle at a later time since the data indicate that sowing late in the season may increase *P. solenopsis* infestation.

2. Evaluating the indicators of attraction by *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at four roselle planting dates:

The data displayed in Table (1) illustrate that the fourth planting date on May 27th exhibited greater values for each of the evaluated variables: the quantity ratio of *P. solenopsis* individuals, crowding density, attraction index, and prevalence

index. This data suggested that *P. solenopsis* individuals displayed a preference towards the fourth planting date over the other planting dates in both seasons. In contrast, the non-preference index for *P. solenopsis* individuals at the fourth planting date on May 27th was comparatively lower as compared to the other three planting dates, as illustrated in Figure (3). The first planting date on April 14th did not display preference by *P. solenopsis* individuals when compared to the other planting dates during both seasons, evidenced by lower estimates of average number of *P. solenopsis* individuals (quantity ratio), attraction index, crowding density, and prevalence index (Table 1). The non-preference index was significantly increasing for the first planting date compared to other planting dates tested for *P. solenopsis* individuals' preference. The quantity ratio and prevalence indices of *P. solenopsis* individuals at four planting dates were summarized in Figure (3). The fourth planting date on May 27th was the highest in quantity ratio with the lowest estimate of prevalence index, while the first planting date on April 14th was the lowest in quantity ratio with the highest estimate of prevalence index, as shown in Figure (3). It is clear that the environmental conditions prevailing at the time of the first planting on April 14th were unsuitable and unfavorable for the growth, activity, and development of the insect, which led to a decrease in insect numbers and a lack of infestation.

Figure (2): Violin plot showing the overall mean number of mealybug individuals of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* per leaf and the average percentage of damaged leaves during the four roselle planting dates assessed in the two seasons (2022 and 2023).

Figure (3): The average quantity ratio and prevalence index of mealybug individuals of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* between all planting dates in both seasons (2022 and 2023).

Table (1): The dispersal and attractiveness of mealybug individuals of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* across the four planting dates were evaluated using a range of metrics in the subsequent two seasons (2022 and 2023).

Planting dates Indices	Season	First date at April 14 th	Second date at April 29 th	Third date at May 13 th	Fourth date at May 27 th
A	2022	9.02	14.49	16.60	18.74
	2023	9.60	15.84	19.39	22.03
QR	2022	15.33	24.62	28.20	31.84
	2023	14.35	23.69	29.01	32.95
AI	2022	0.76	0.99	1.06	1.12
	2023	0.73	0.97	1.07	1.14
M*	2022	12.34	21.45	23.02	25.31
	2023	12.86	21.26	26.97	28.02
NPI	2022	49.85	49.75	49.72	49.68
	2023	49.86	49.76	49.71	49.67
PI	2022	-23.97	-0.76	6.02	12.04
	2023	-27.06	-2.69	7.42	13.72

Definitions: A = count of mealybug individuals of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* per leaf for every planting date; QR = quantity ratio; AI = attractiveness index; M* = mean crowding index; NPI = non-preference index; PI = prevalence index.

3. Principal Component Analysis of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* estimates and their relationship to different planting dates:

By lowering the dimensionality of complicated datasets, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a potent multivariate statistical method, may highlight important correlations and patterns (Getu *et al.*, 2024). In order to determine the main causes of variability and the connections between the treatments, this study used PCA to examine the effects of four distinct roselle planting dates on mealybug numbers over the two consecutive seasons. The PCA biplots for both seasons (Figure 4) exhibited a consistent and unambiguous pattern. In both years, the first planting date was clearly separated from the other three and located in the upper right quadrant of the biplot, indicating its unique set of mealybug counts. Conversely, the second, third, and fourth planting dates were clustered together in the lower right quadrant, and the strong grouping indicates that the later planting dates produced more

similar mealybug counts, which were distinctly different from the early planting dates. The vectors in the biplots also indicate these relationships, the first planting date being aligned with a vector pointing upwards, and the later planting dates being aligned with vectors pointing downwards.

The scree plots from both the 2022 and 2023 growing seasons indicated that the first principal component (PCA 1) explained most of the variance. In the first growing season (2022), PCA 1 explained 85.82% of the variance, and PCA 2 contributed an additional 9.88%, for a cumulative total of 95.7% (Figure 5). Likewise, in the second growing season (2023), PCA 1 and PCA 2 accounted for 84.13% and 9.44% of the variance, respectively, totaling 93.56% (Fig. 5). The very high explained variance for the first two principal components indicates that these are a good measure of data. The consistent findings from the PCA over the two different growing seasons strongly indicate that planting date is an

important driver of variability in mealybug estimates. Notably, the clear distinction of the first planting date from the other three clearly indicates that it influenced the mealybug counts significantly.

4. Hierarchical clustering analysis:

4.1. A dendrogram from hierarchical cluster analysis of maize cultivars was applied to estimate the relationships between numbers of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* individuals at four planting dates:

Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) is a powerful statistical technique that can group similar data points together, making it an ideal tool for identifying patterns in complex agricultural datasets. This study aimed to use hierarchical cluster analysis to evaluate the relationships among four different roselle planting dates based on *P. solenopsis* counts during the 2022 and 2023 growing seasons. Hierarchical cluster analysis was visualized in a dendrogram format (Fig. 6) and provides a powerful corroboration of the findings of the mean mealybug counts, as well as PCA.

4.1.1. Temporal clustering of planting dates:

The roselle planting dates in 2022 and 2023 were clearly grouped by the hierarchical cluster analysis, which was displayed in the dendrogram (Figure 6). Since the third and fourth planting dates were the first to be clustered together at the smallest distance, the analysis revealed a

remarkable resemblance between them. The second planting date was then blended with this cluster. The first planting date was the most noticeable, as it clustered off from the others at a somewhat greater distance.

4.1.2. Inter-temporal clustering distances:

The clusters' similarity may be quantified by the distances at which they merged. The distance was comparatively short for the third and fourth planting dates. When the second planting date was combined with these two dates, the distance increased. Its unique character was confirmed when the cluster of the second, third, and fourth dates eventually blended with the first planting date, resulting in the greatest distance, which confirmed the dissimilarity of the first planting date, as illustrated in Figure (6). According to the dendrogram, the first planting date is an anomaly, but the second, third, and fourth planting dates are more closely connected, as seen in Figure (6). The study results conclusively show that one of the most important factors influencing mealybug counts is the timing of hibiscus planting. A clear pattern emerged when the planting dates were successfully categorized using cluster analysis according to their performance. Planting roselle later in the season may result in higher mealybug numbers, as seen by the proximity of the third and fourth planting dates.

Figure (4): PCA biplot showing the association of four planting dates and *Phenacoccus solenopsis* individual counts per leaf in both seasons (2022 and 2023).

Figure (5): Scree plot showing the percentage of explained variance from each principal component for each season (2022 and 2023).

Figure (6): Dendrogram from hierarchical cluster analysis showing the clustering of four planting dates based on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* estimates over two seasons (2022 and 2023).

4.2. Heat maps and hierarchical clustering were used for the evaluation of seven indicators of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* population, damage, and their spread observed on various planting dates of roselle:

The heatmaps, which provide graphical depictions of the relationship among the four roselle planting dates and their associated seven measured parameters for two growing seasons (2022 and 2023), can be observed in Figure (7). The dendrogram was created based on the similarity coefficient for the four planting dates over the two seasons. Similar planting dates (For example, similar infestations) and similar parameters (for example, parameters

with a significant association) were grouped by their respective cluster dendrograms. The heat map depicts the Euclidean distances between the four planting dates (Rows) and seven variables (Columns). The hierarchical clustering for the seven parameters is shown in the top dendrogram, and then the clustering for the four planting dates is shown in the left dendrogram. The numbers used in the matrix depict the similarities and dissimilarities in some studied characteristics, with the use of the colour gradient represented from dark red to dark blue. The matrix numbers, which were used to display this gradient colour, were intentionally made more transparent (Figure 7).

Figure (7): The Euclidean distances between the four roselle planting dates are shown on the heatmap of a dendrogram. Dates of planting are on the Y-axis. The X-axis displays the seven factors that are being evaluated at each planting time. The column and row dendrograms, respectively, demonstrate the clustering of the assessed parameters and the planting dates. In the graphic legend (scale), dark blue denoted metrics that were rising, while dark red denoted metrics that were declining.

4.2.3. Mixed interpretation:

By combining the heatmap and dendrograms together, you could say that the first planting date had a unique pattern of infestation over both seasons. The dark blue hue of the non-preference index reveals that mealybugs had a very negative effect on the plants, while the solid red colours for the majority of this row's criteria show that they had a less detrimental effect. In contrast to the later planting dates, which tended to have higher levels of infestation, this pattern provides excellent visual support for what would amount to a non-chemical pest management option, which would be to change the planting schedule. It is clear from the heat map that early planting originally appeared to be a highly effective strategy for reducing pest infestation.

Low values for pest-related indices paired with higher values for the non-preference index indicate that the roselle plants either A) went through a peak pest population period without host-plant interaction or B) developed a mechanism to show unfavourable physiological and/or chemical attributes or properties that deterred the mealybugs, and C) perhaps due to the environmental circumstances, were unsuitable for the insect's activity and growth at the time; this occurred on the initial planting date. Consistent with the research findings and aims, all subsequent planting dates, especially the fourth planting date, displayed high levels of insect infestation. The fourth planting date, particularly and consistently, is representative of higher levels of infestation. Reasons for high pest abundance levels can stem from several factors: A) The timing of the later planting dates was likely closely aligned with the period when mealybugs reached peak populations and/or levels of activity. B) Secondly, the plants could have been at a susceptible development stage when the

later planting dates took place, when the environment was favourable for insect populations, and C) the roselle plants' phenological stage during the height of mealybug activity may also have a role. In this context, the second, third, and fourth planting dates all cluster together, indicating that they were related to pest pressure similarly, but given their order, also differentiates the pressure level of pest exploitation. The later the planting date is, the more susceptible the plant will be to pest pressure.

Although roselle (*H. sabdariffa*) is a valuable crop, insect pests like mealybugs sometimes hinder its output. Since these pests have the potential to seriously affect the roselle plants' productivity and health, successful cultivation depends on efficient pest management. In order to maximize output and guarantee a steady supply of this priceless crop, these issues must be resolved. Gálvez-Marroquín *et al.* (2023) stated that the cotton mealybug, *P. solenopsis*, has been documented to cause considerable damage to roselle, with infestation levels between 14% and 86%. The results demonstrated that roselle plants planted later had a higher percentage of leaves damaged by infection and a higher mealybug population density. However, both the mealybug population and the percentage of damaged leaves are lowest on the first planting date. Mealybug numbers rise, and the percentage of damaged leaves increases with later planting dates. This suggests that early roselle planting might be a simple and effective strategy to lower crop loss and mealybug infestation.

Each of the seven assessed variables—the quantity ratio of *P. solenopsis* individuals, crowding density, attraction index, and prevalence index showed higher values on May 27th, the fourth planting date, according to the results. In contrast to

the other three planting dates, the non-preference index was lower. However, when compared to the other planting dates in both seasons, the first planting date on April 14th did not show a preference by *P. solenopsis* individuals. This was demonstrated by lower estimates of all evaluated variables, with the exception of the non-preference index, which was significantly increasing for the first planting date.

By applying the multivariate analysis applications, the impact of four different roselle planting dates (First, second, third, and fourth) on the *P. solenopsis* counts across two growing seasons (2022 and 2023) was examined in this study using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). A dataset of mealybug estimations for four planting dates was used for the research. The first two principal components (PCA 1 and PCA 2) accounted for 95.7% and 93.56% of the total data variance in the first and second seasons, respectively, according to the scree plots for both seasons. In both years, the biplots consistently showed a distinct division between the first planting date and the next three (second, third, and fourth). The earliest planting date was located in the upper quadrant, while later dates were clustered in the lower quadrant. This study reveals the important influence of planting date on mealybug populations and demonstrates the usefulness of principal component analysis (PCA) in agricultural research to uncover underlying patterns.

The planting dates (1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th) were grouped based on the overall similarity of mealybug numbers using a hierarchical cluster analysis based on Euclidean distance in two years (2022 and 2023). The third and fourth planting dates were consistently the most similar to one another, forming a compact cluster, according to the ensuing dendrogram. The initial planting date

was the most noticeable, clustering apart from all the others; however, this cluster later combined with the second planting date. These associations are quantified by the distance values at the top of the dendrogram, which show a distinct hierarchy of similarity. According to the results, mealybug numbers are significantly influenced by the roselle planting date, with later planting dates creating a more uniform group.

The heatmaps elucidate the relationships discussed previously in more detail. Across both seasons, the fourth planting date demonstrated consistently high levels of mealybug infestation. This is easily seen by the dark blue cells in the row associated with the "fourth" planting date on the heatmap. The high infestation was characterised by high values for every parameter measured: mean crowding intensity, damaged leaves percentage, prevalence index, attraction index, quantity ratio, and number of mealybug individuals. The non-preference index was the exception, which is clearly illustrated with its low value (red cell) in the fourth planting date. In 2022, the second and third planting dates were most similar to each other among the planting dates. In 2023, it was the third and fourth planting dates that were most similar. This suggests that the optimal time to minimize the peak *P. solenopsis* populations is likely to change slightly from year to year.

Another interesting result was the opposite relationship between the non-preference index and the other infestation parameters. The results demonstrate that a lower non-preference index (Meaning greater preference for the mealybugs) led to a greater degree of infestation. This supports using the non-preference index as an indicator of a plant's susceptibility or resistance to mealybugs in subsequent field studies. The evidence

was especially strong that this link existed because the fourth planting date had both the lowest non-preference index and the highest infestation level of all the planting dates. There exists limited data in the current scientific literature regarding the impact of the time of planting roselle on mealybug numbers and its indicators of distribution and attractiveness. It has been scientifically documented that early planting of roselle generally allows for better growth of the crop and reduces pest issues, while late planting may increase pest susceptibility because the crop's overall health is less vigorous. This illustrates the importance of planting dates in addressing both crop yield and pest populations. The growth of roselle is also dependent on environmental conditions (Rie *et al.*, 2009).

Nnebue *et al.* (2014) concluded that early planting of roselle would be less impacted by pest pressures, as the crop would be more vigorous and could suffer less destruction from infestations, as opposed to crops planted later in the season. Based on other host plants, Awadalla *et al.* (2018) mentioned that the highest counts were observed in February for the last planting of tomato during September, further confirming a link between the time of planting and pest impactation. Research, as previously indicated with cotton plants, shows a prevalence of mealybug infestations with increased planting date. Soares and Silva (2003) indicated that increased mealybug counts during the time of planting may result in decreased cotton yields due to the pest's impact on plant health. Soares *et al.* (2006) went on to say that increased cotton pest populations were noted during a planting period in January. The cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) increased from the planting date and was likely associated with decreased

cotton yields. According to Adams *et al.* (2013), planting cotton in mid-April resulted in fewer pest and insecticide applications than planting in early June, which improved crop health and yield.

There is evidence that changes in planting dates can be an affordable option to reduce pest pressure in other crops. In contrast to early cotton, early planting may change the timing of the life cycle of insect pests and host plants to reduce pests (Asif *et al.*, 2023). In this example, early planting on June 4th resulted in more fruit per plant (43.6%) than the later dates but yielded a higher biomass and sepal yield of 395.33 kg/ha (Gholam and Moosavi, 2012). Changing a planting date can have a similar effect on timing the life cycle of the insect guest plant, as demonstrated in the example of cotton. Compared to later planting, the early planting produced a higher yield and significantly reduced insect pests, such as bollworms and jassids (Asif *et al.*, 2023). Araujo *et al.* (2019) referred to the planting window as the time that peach crops were planted in relation to the time of the pest dialogue.

Generally, the increased infestation levels in the later planting dates support a possible and practical pest management strategy. If growers are able to plant roselle earlier, they may be able to take advantage of potentially naturally avoiding *P. solenopsis* peak activity periods. This, in turn, might help to minimize or eliminate the use of chemicals for pest management. Because of this, choosing a planting date strategically is an important non-chemical part of an integrated pest management (IPM) strategy. To fine-tune such a technique, it is crucial to comprehend local, year-specific temperature trends, as seen by the slight variations in the clustering of later planting dates between the two years.

This research indicates that initiating roselle cultivation on April 14th serves

as an effective agronomic strategy to mitigate *P. solenopsis* infestations, with the timing of planting identified as a crucial factor in the management of roselle pests. The findings revealed a direct correlation between delayed planting dates and elevated *P. solenopsis* populations, resulting in increased damage to the plants. Early planting has been identified as a significant cultural control method, successfully diminishing pest pressure and fostering conditions that are less conducive to mealybug proliferation. The strong association of the non-preference index with the early planting date suggests that the plants may have been either less appealing or more resilient to pest attacks during that phase.

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